

PYTHON DASTURI YARATILISH TARIXI VA IMKONIYATLARI

Mahbubov Mohirjon

Qo'qon DPI, "Matematika-informatika" yo'nalishi

3- bosqich talabasi

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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tezisdagi Python daturining yaratilish tarixi va ushbu dasturlash tilining imkoniyatlari haqida qisqacha ma'lumot berilgan.*

Pythonni tarixi

Python Guido van Rossum tomonidan sakson va sakkizinchi yillarda Niderlandiyadagi Matematika va informatika ilmiy tadqiqot institutida ishlab chiqildi.

Python ABC, Modula-3, C, C ++, Algol-68, SmallTalk va Unix shell kabi boshqa ko'plab tillardan va boshqa skript tillaridan olingan.

Python mualliflik huquqi bilan himoyalangan. Perl kabi, Python manba kodi endi GNU General Public License (GPL) ostida mavjud.

Python hozirda institutning asosiy rivojlanish jamoasi tomonidan faoliyat yuritmoqda, garchi Guido van Rossum hali ham o'z taraqqiyotini boshqarishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Python ([ˈpɑɪθ (ə)n] — *payton, piton*) — turli sohalar uchun yuqori darajadagi umumiy maqsadli dasturlash tili. Uning dizayn falsafasi muhim chekinishdan foydalangan holda kodning o'qilishiga urg'u beradi. Uning til konstruksiyalari va obyektga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvi dasturchilarga kichik va yirik loyihalar uchun aniq, mantiqiy kod yozishda yordam berishga qaratilgan. Shuningdek Python sun'iy intellekt hamda ma'lumotlar muhandisiligi sohalarining tili hisoblanadi.

Python deyarli barcha platformalarda ishlay oladi, xususan Windows, Linux, Mac OS X, Palm OS, Mac OS va boshqalar shular jumlasidandir. Python Microsoft.NET platformasi uchun yozilgan realizatsiyasi ham mavjud bo'lib, uning nomi — IronPython dasturlash muhitidir.

Guido van Rossum 1980-yillarning oxirida ABC dasturlash tilining davomchisi sifatida Python ustida ishlay boshladi va birinchi marta 1991-yilda Python 0.9.0 versiyasini ommaga e'lon qildi¹.

Python dasturlash tiliga bo'lgan talab yildan yilga oshib bormoqda. CodingDojo¹ portalining tadqiqotlariga ko'ra, 2020—2021-yillarda aynan Python tilida dasturlovchi mutaxassislariga eng ko'p talab bo'lgan

Pythonni ishlatadigan dasturlar

Wikipedia — botlarni yozish uchun ishlatadi.

- Civilization IV — Yaxshi strategiya o'yin.

Pythonni ishlatadigan kompaniyalar

- Kosmik teleskop instituti
- NASA
- Google
- DreamWorks
- Industrial Light & Magic
- Firaxis Games
- Apple Computer
- CCP

Python xususiyatlari:

Pythonning xususiyati quyidagilarni o'z ichiga oladi:

- **O'qish oson:** Python nisbatan kam kalit so'zlar, oddiy tuzilish va aniq belgilangan sintaksisga ega. Bu o'rganuvchini qisqa vaqt ichida yodlab olish imkonini beradi.
- **O'qish oson:** Python kodi juda aniq va ko'zga ko'rinadigan bo'ladi.
- **Oson ishlash:** Pythonning muvaffaqiyati – manba kodi juda oson.
- **Keng standart kutubxona:** Pythonning eng qudratli jihatlaridan biri kutubxonaning asosiy qismi juda portativ va UNIX, Windows va Macintosh-da o'zaro faoliyat platformalar bilan mos keladi.
- **Interaktiv usul:** Pythonda ishlashda terminalda ishlash uchun juda qulay terminalda test qilib ko'rsa bo'ladi.
- **Portativ:** Python keng apparat platformalarida ishlaydi va barcha platformalarda bir xil interfeysga ega.
- **Kengaytirilgan:** Python tarjimoniga past darajadagi modullarni qo'shishingiz mumkin. Ushbu modullar dasturchilarni o'zlarining vositalarini samaraliroq bo'lishiga qo'shish yoki sozlash imkonini beradi.
- **Ma'lumotlar bazasi:** Python barcha ma'lumotlar bazasini qo'llab quvvatlaydi.
- **GUI dasturlash:** Python Windows MFC, Unix, X Window kabi platformalarga GUI dasturlar tuzishni qo'llab quvvatlaydi
- **Moslashuvchan:** Python, qobiq buyruq fayliga qaraganda katta dasturlarga yanada yaxshi tuzilish va qo'llab-quvvatlash imkonini beradi.

Yuqorida aytib o'tilgan xususiyatlardan tashqari, Pythonda yaxshi xususiyatlarining katta ro'yxati bor, ularning ko'pi quyida keltirilgan:

- Funktsional va tuzilgan dasturiy usullarni va OOP ni qo'llab-quvvatlash.
- Ushbu buyruq fayli sifatida ishlatilishi mumkin yoki katta ilovalar yaratish uchun byte-kodga to'planishi mumkin.
- Juda yuqori darajadagi dinamik ma'lumotlar turlari va dinamik turdagi tekshiruvlarni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi.
- Avtomatik chiqindilarni to'plashni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi.
- C, C ++, MAQOMOTI, ActiveX, CORBA va Java bilan osonlik bilan bog'lanishi mumkin.

Misol. Funksiyali amallarni bajarilishi

Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license()" for more information.

```
>>> y=-5
>>> abs(y) 5
>>> x=12.32568
>>> round(x) 12
>>> y=13.652
>>> round(y) 14
>>> round(13.652,2)
13.65
```

```
>>> a=2
>>> b=3
>>> pow(a,b) 8
>>> a=5
>>> b=2
>>> x,y=divmod(a,b)
>>> x 2
>>> y 1
>>>
```

Ta'minlash operatori Ma'lum bir ifodaning natijasi biror o'zgaruvchiga ta'minlash uchun Python dasturlash tilida "=" belgisi bilan ishlatiladi va uning umumiy ko'rinishi quyidagicha: =; Python dasturlash tilida taminlash operatori amallar yordamida ham ishlatiladi. Qo'shish qiymat berish bilan (+=); ayirish qiymat berish bilan (-=); ko'paytirish, qiymat berish bilan (*=); bo'lish qiymat berish bilan (/=); bo'lish qoldig'ini olish qiymat berish bilan (%=) va boshqalar. Bu holatlarning umumiy ko'rinishi: =; s+=x; ning ma'nosi s=s+x; Ta'minlash operatorini ishlash jarayoni tushunarli bo'lishi uchun, ularni interaktiv rejimda sinab ko'ramiz.

Misol. Ta'minlash operatorida foydalanish

Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license()" for more information.

```
>>> x=5
>>> y=2
>>> x*=y
>>> x
```

```
10
>>> x/=2
>>> x 5.0
>>> x%=y
>>> x 1.0
```

Python dasturlash tilida $s+=x$ amali $s=x$ amaliga teng kuchli hisoblanadi, $s=x+$ va $s=x++$ amallari python dasturlash tilida aniqlanmagan.

Python dasturlash tilida matematik funksiyalar

Python dasturlash tili tarkibida mavjud bo'lgan matematik funksiyalar standart funksiyalar deb ataladi. Ifodalar tarkibidagi funksiyalarni Python dasturlash tilida ifodalash uchun standart funksiyalardan foydalaniladi. Funksiyalarni python dasturlash tilida ifodalash uchun ularni argumentlarini albatta qavsga olib yozish kerak. Python dasturlash tilida matematik funksiyalardan foydalanish uchun albatta python tili tarkibidagi matematik funksiyalar kutubxonasiga murojat qilish kerak. Matematik funksiyalar kutubxonasiga murojat qilish quyidagicha. f

from math import*

Python dasturlash tili tarkibidagi matematik funksiyalar yozilishi quyidagi ro'yxat asosida amalga oshiriladi.

No	Python dasturlash tilida ifodalanishi	Matematik ifodalanishi
1	trunc(x)	Sonning butun qismi trunc(5.8)=5, trunc(- 5.8)=-5
2	sqrt(x)	x ning kvadrat ildiz
3	log(x), log2(x), log10(x)	
4	log(x,a)	
5	sin(x), cos(x), tan(x)	Sinx, cosx, tgx trigonometrik funksiyalar
6	asin(x), acos(x), atan(x)	Arcsinx, arccosx, arctgx teskari trigonometrik funksiyalar
7	atan2(x,y)	
8	degrees(x)	Radiandan gradusga o'tkazish funksiyasi
9	radians(x)	Gradusdan radianga o'tkazish funksiyasi
10	sinh(x), cosh(x), tanh(x)	Giperbolik Sinx, cosx ,tgx trigonometrik funksiyalar
11	asinh(x), acosh(x), atanh(x)	Giperbolik Arcsinx, arccosx, arctgx teskari trigonometrik funksiyalar
12	hypot(x,y)	Katetlari x va y bo'lgan to'g'ri burchakli uchburchakning getatinuzasini topish
13	factorial(x)	X faktorialni hisoblash funksiyasi
14	gamma	x ning gamma funksiyasi
15	pi	π soni $\pi=3.1415...$
16	e	Eksponentsial funksiya $e=2.71...$

Matematik funksiyalarning bajarilish jarayoni, matematikada qanday bo'lsa python dasturlash tilida ham xuddi shunday amalga oshiriladi. Matematik funksiyalarni ishlash jarayoni tushunarli bo'lishi uchun, ularni interaktiv rejimda sinab ko'ramiz. Chunki interaktiv rejim bir vaqtning uzida natija qaytaradi.

Foydalanilgan saytlar ro'yxati:

1. <http://cplusplus> – Python tilida mavjud konstruksiyalar ta'rifi, ishlatish na'munalari bilan keltirilgan.
2. Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Prospects for the development of professional training of students of professional educational institutions using electronic educational resources in the environment of digital transformation." *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research* 3.10 (2022): 158-162.
3. Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "The value of open mass competitions in the process of digitalization of extracurricular activities of schoolchildren." *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal* 3.10 (2022): 338-344.
4. Jo'rayev, Muzaffarjon. "Professional ta'lim jarayonida fanlararo uzvilik va uzliksizlikni ta'minlash o'quvchilari kasbiy tayyorgarligining muhim omili sifatida." *Zamonaviy dunyoda amaliy fanlar: Muammolar va yechimlar* 1.29 (2022): 43-46.
5. Juraev, M. M. "OA Qo'ysinov Description of the methodological basis for ensuring interdisciplinary continuity of the subject "Computer Science and Information Technology" in vocational education." *JournalNX-A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed* 7.10 (2021).
6. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Description of the Methodological Basis for Ensuring Interdisciplinary Continuity of the Subject" *Computer Science and Information TECHNOLOGY in Vocational Education.* *JournalNX* 7.10: 223-225.
7. Khasanov, A. R. (2022). LEARNING IS A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH AS A CONTENT UPDATE STEP. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 217-223.
8. Khasanov, A. R. (2022). Development of information competence of future informatics teachers as a pedagogical problem. *Open Access Repository*, 9(12), 73-79.
9. Xasanov, A. R. (2021, May). USE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING COMPUTER SCIENCE. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 198-199).
10. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "CURRENT STATUS OF THE SCIENCE OF INFORMATICS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION SYSTEM, EXISTING PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS, PRINCIPLES AND CONTENT OF THE SCIENCE ORGANIZATION." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 327-331.
11. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Professional Educational Institutions Theoretical and Practical Basis of Development of the Content of Pedagogical Activity of Teachers of Information and Information Technologies." *Open Access Repository* 9.12 (2022): 85-89.
12. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Experience Of Cambridge Curricula In Ensuring The Continuity Of Curricula In The Field Of "Computer Science And Information Technology" In The System Of Professional Education." *The American Journal of Interdisciplinary Innovations and Research* 3.11 (2021): 26-32.
13. Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Theoretical and practical principles of improving the content of the pedagogical activity of ICT teachers of professional educational institutions in the conditions of information of education." (2022).
14. Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Methodological foundations for improving the content of training future ict teachers in the conditions of digital transformation of education." (2022): 9-11.

15.Melikyzievich, Siddikov Ilkhom, et al. "THE METHOD OF REFERENCE TESTS FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF DIGITAL DEVICES." International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education 14.7 (2022).

16.Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Designing an electronic didactic environment to ensure interdisciplinary integration in the teaching of" Informatics and information technologies" during professional education." Confrencea 11.11 (2023): 78-82.

17.Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon, and Aroyev Dilshod Davronovich. "INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION IS AN IMPORTANT PART OF DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS." Open Access Repository 9.1 (2023): 93-101.

18.Juraev, M. M. "ZY Xudoyberdiyev Theoretical analysis of the continuity model of computer science and information technology in the System of professional education." European Scholar Journal (ESJ)//ISSN (E): 2660-5562.

19.Xudayberdiyev, Zayniddin Yavkachevich, and Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich Juraev. "Theoretical analysis of the continuity model of computer science and information technology in the system of professional education." (2021).

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